

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck and waterfront at Skeppsholmen, Stockholm.

by

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Dendro.dk report 54 : 2017

Commissioned by Jim Hansson, Swedish National Maritime Museums.

Twenty-two samples from Skeppsholmen, Stockholm, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. Twelve are from ship timbers while ten are from bulwark constructions. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

Skeppsholmen, Stockholm

The ship

All the 12 samples from the ship are of *Quercus sp.*, oak. Samples P9 and P11 originally are assumed to be from two separate planks, but on examination during this analysis it could be seen that these are two pieces from the same original timber (see fig. 1). So, there are just 11 samples in all from the ship.

Nine of the 11 samples from the ship are dated. Sapwood was preserved on seven of these, and bark edge on three.

Sample P9, plank

A sample from a ship's plank has complete sapwood to bark edge preserved. It has not been possible to detect whether the bark ring was fully formed or whether the ring stopped its growth during the growth season. The bark ring was formed in AD 1612. The tree from which this plank was made was felled between summer AD 1612 and spring AD 1613 (see fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Sample P9 and P11 are from the same original timber. Only sample P9 was analysed therefore.

Fig. 2. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. The chronological position of the dated samples. Green are oak, orange are pine, and the blue is probably spruce.

Sample P, floor riser

The sample from a floor riser (*kattspår*) also has complete sapwood to bark edge preserved. The bark ring on this sample has just begun to form, which means that the tree that the sample comes from was felled just at the beginning of the growing season. This tree was felled in spring AD 1613 (see fig. 2).

Sample P10 framing timber

Complete sapwood to bark edge is also preserved on sample P10. The bark ring on this sample is fully formed, indicating that the tree was felled in the winter half-year. This tree was felled in winter AD 1613-14 (see fig. 2).

The felling dates for the trees that the remaining dated oak samples from the ship come from are estimated, accounting for missing sapwood (see fig. 2 and catalogue). Their dating falls neatly within the dating of the three samples with bark edge preserved, and thus probably all come from the original building phase of the ship.

The bulwark

Eight of the ten samples from the bulwark or harbour front are of *Pinus sp.*, pine while the remaining two are probably *Picea sp./Larix sp.*, spruce/larch. Eight samples from the bulwark are dated (see fig. 2 and catalogue). Five of the dated samples have bark edge preserved while two have possible bark edge. Sample P6 from an upright post is from a tree felled winter AD 1728-29. Sample P5, also from an upright post, might have been felled at the same time.

Sample P12 from an upright post, with the engraving “x13x8x”, is from a pine tree felled winter AD 1743-44.

An upright pole from a crane foundation is from a pine tree felled possibly in AD 1745-46 (unconfirmed bark edge).

Two horizontal timbers, both from a crane foundation, are from pine trees felled in winter AD 1774-75 and after AD 1775 respectively (see fig. 2). A single dated spruce sample is from a tree possibly felled in AD 1774-75 (bark edge not confirmed).

Clearly, several phases of building works at the waterside are represented in the conifer datings; works take place in the 1720s, again in the 1740s and finally in the 1770s.

				SE06004a	SE060029	SE06006a	SE06009a	SE06003a	SE06010a	SE06007a	SE06008a	Z207003a	Z2070019	Z207009a	Z207007a	Z207002a	Z207006a	Z207008a	Z207004a	Z207011a
		P15	SE06004a	*	4,55	4,43	3,43	-	-	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
SE06 M001	Gr 1	P3	SE060029	4,55	*	3,63	4,34	-	1,66	-	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P4	SE06006a	4,43	3,63	*	5,29	-	-	-	1,23	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P2	SE06009a	3,43	4,34	5,29	*	-	-	-	-	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P12	SE06003a	-	-	-	-	*	7,4	4,06	2,33	-	1,91	1,1	-	-	1,48	-	2,05	1,52
SE06 M002	Gr 2	P16	SE06010a	-	1,66	-	-	7,4	*	5,57	4,49	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P6	SE06007a	-	-	-	-	4,06	5,57	*	5,54	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P5	SE06008a	\	-	1,23	-	2,33	4,49	5,54	*	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\
		P1	Z207003a	\	\	\	\	-	\	\	\	*	4,00	1,18	2,82	1,22	2,19	2,37	3,21	2,8
Z207M002	Ship group	P21	Z2070019	\	\	\	\	1,91	\	\	\	4,00	*	5,38	5,44	2,04	2,48	3,98	3,51	3,19
		P22	Z207009a	\	\	\	\	1,1	\	\	\	1,18	5,38	*	3,1	1,35	1,2	2,48	3,47	1,28
		P20	Z207007a	\	\	\	\	-	\	\	\	2,82	5,44	3,1	*	5,05	-	3,84	1,47	2,19
		P9	Z207002a	\	\	\	\	-	\	\	\	1,22	2,04	1,35	5,05	*	3,52	2,56	1,44	2,61
		P7	Z207006a	\	\	\	\	1,48	\	\	\	2,19	2,48	1,2	-	3,52	*	4,7	3,61	4,5
		P10	Z207008a	\	\	\	\	-	\	\	\	2,37	3,98	2,48	3,84	2,56	4,7	*	3,85	4,77
		P17	Z207004a	\	\	\	\	2,05	\	\	\	3,21	3,51	3,47	1,47	1,44	3,61	3,85	*	5,29
		P8	Z207011a	\	\	\	\	1,52	\	\	\	2,8	3,19	1,28	2,19	2,61	4,5	4,77	5,29	*

Table 1. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation (*t*-value) between the tree-ring curves from each of the dated samples from the site with each other. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values. Green are oak, orange are pine, blue is probably spruce.

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Provenance

In table 1 the correlation (t -value) of the dated tree-ring curves with each other is shown. Three groups can be identified and three averages have therefore been made.

The tree-ring curves from the dated oak samples from the ship form one group and an average (Z207M002) of 201 years in length is calculated. It covers the period AD 1413-1613. The correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe is shown in table 2. The oak from the Skeppsholmen ship is achieving highest correlation (t -values) with material from the Vasa ship, currently under analysis, in the research project TIMBER (ERC project no. 677152) based at Copenhagen University. It is emerging that the timbers from Vasa are forming several groups, and the groups that the Skeppsholmen ship's oaks are dating with are probably from Småland.

Filenames	-	-	Ship group Z207M002	
-	start	dates	AD 1413	
-	dates	end	AD 1613	
Z0921M02	AD 1424	AD 1609	9.45	Vasa hull planks mostly 11 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z0921M03	AD 1341	AD 1625	6.85	Vasa mostly frames 9 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z113M002	AD 1506	AD 1620	6.56	Culla Wreck Cork Ireland BARREL 3 timbers (Daly 2014)
BAT6047a	AD 1426	AD 1586	6.25	Batavia Western Australia ship-frame (Daly 2016b)
Z109M001	AD 1437	AD 1597	5.73	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers [Daly 2013]
EP41592	AD 1390	AD 1592	5.53	Stirling Castle Scotland IMPORTS episode 4 [Crone pers comm]
6094M002	AD 1450	AD 1660	5.46	Funder kirke later material 4 timbers [Daly 2002]
Z203M002	AD 1364	AD 1538	5.07	Elefanten ship 3 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z092101b	AD 1424	AD 1607	6.77	Vasa ship bitt midships aft upper canon deck [Daly in prep]
Z092118a	AD 1452	AD 1568	6.72	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D16 mid right [Daly in prep]
Z092150a	AD 1436	AD 1608	6.65	Vasa D51 ceiling right side GP4 ÖB ps [Daly in prep]
Z092114a	AD 1357	AD 1612	6.59	Vasa frame at GP9 D37 lower gundeck sb [Daly in prep]
Z092148a	AD 1509	AD 1622	6.57	Vasa D49 frame GP4 ÖB ps forward of two [Daly in prep]
Z0921179	AD 1470	AD 1593	6.46	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D15 upper right [Daly in prep]
Z092120a	AD 1477	AD 1607	5.93	Vasa D18 ceiling plank GP12 top left [Daly in prep]
Z092111a	AD 1440	AD 1593	5.56	Vasa outer plank GP24 D13 upper gundeck [Daly in prep]
Z092198a	AD 1454	AD 1588	5.31	Vasa D99 sill GP1 ÖB sb [Daly in prep]
Z0921221	AD 1504	AD 1586	5.28	Vasa D20 outer hull plank GP12 mid right [Daly in prep]
Z0921779	AD 1471	AD 1585	5.16	Vasa D78 frame GP21 ÖB sb forward of 2 [Daly in prep]

Table 2. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the oak average curve for the ship and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Two groups are apparent in the conifer material from Skeppsholmen. Group 1 consists of three pines, but the dated spruce sample probably belongs with this group geographically. The average SE06M001 is made from the three pine tree-ring curves in the group. It is 120 years long and covers the period AD1656-1775. As can be seen in table 3, the average is dating with a range of tree-ring datasets for Scandinavia and group 1 is probably from trees that grew in the wider Stockholm hinterland.

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Filenames	-	-	Group 1 SE06M001	Group 2 SE06M002	
-	start	dates	AD 1656	AD 1614	
-	dates	end	AD 1775	AD 1748	
SWED_GTA	AD 1636	AD 1855	8.49	3.80	Götaland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_AAL	AD 1068	AD 1827	7.63	-	Aaland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED302	AD 1582	AD 1995	7.08	-	Naemdoe Stockholm archipelago [Lars Ake Larsson]
Swed_mal	AD 1083	AD 1992	7.04	-	Malardalen Gotland Sweden [Alf Bräthen]
SWED_GOT	AD 1124	AD 1987	6.98	-	Gotland [Bartholin pers comm]
B027pine bl.	AD 1715	AD 1823	6.57	\	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine blue 3 timbers [Daly 2016a]
SWED304	AD 1667	AD 1779	6.46	-	Sisshammar [Tomas Andreason]
SWED_GRV	AD 1469	AD 1840	6.07	-	Gravsten [Bartholin pers comm]
bjørvikM001	AD 1695	AD 1823	5.81	-	Two Bjørvik ships 2 timbers (Daly 2011)
SWED022	AD 1127	AD 1987	5.58	-	Gotland [Fritz Schweingruber]
DANPIN01	AD 1380	AD 1853	5.42	-	Copenhagen B&W Grunden all [Daly 1997a & b]
99700010	AD 552	AD 1979	-	5.00	Norway middle [Thun pers comm]
00000060	AD 1482	AD 1954	-	5.02	Norway [Eidem+Aanstadt]
B027pine N-	AD 1457	AD 1785	-	5.02	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine N-S structure 3 timbers [Daly 2016a]
99200010	AD 871	AD 1986	-	5.05	Norway south-east [Thun pers comm]
N008m001	AD 1603	AD 1748	-	5.43	Jernbanetorget Oslo 2 timbers (Daly 2009)
SANDY1	AD 1665	AD 1777	-	5.53	78 Sandy Lane Woking Surrey [C Tyers pers comm]
FMV0001B	AD 1571	AD 1731	-	5.58	Finland Vaasan [Zetterberg pers comm]
B027pine N-	AD 1457	AD 1802	-	5.71	Gammel Strand Copenhagen pine N-S structure filtered 4 timbers [Daly 2016a]
SWED_DAL	AD 1001	AD 1852	-	5.85	Dalarna [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED305	AD 1450	AD 2002	-	5.93	Bjorbo Dalarna [Torbjorn Axelson]
SWED023	AD 1107	AD 1827	-	6.41	Jamtland [Fritz Schweingruber]
DURQSQ01	AD 1585	AD 1900	-	6.49	Durham Cathedral 11 timbers [C Tyers pers comm]
ccb7	AD 1627	AD 1847	-	6.88	Christ Church Oxford Barn Phase [DHR/DM/AML]
SELTYP_P	AD 1424	AD 1938	-	7.37	Selbu & Tydal Norway Pine 13 trees [Eidem 1953]
dalpinus	AD 931	AD 1888	-	7.44	Dalarna [Eggertsson pers comm]
SELBU_P2	AD 1424	AD 1938	-	7.45	Selbu Norway Pine 9 trees [Eidem 1953]
SWED_HL1	AD 1001	AD 1861	-	7.49	Helsingland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_JM2	AD 1305	AD 1827	-	8.18	Sweden Jämtland pine [Bartholin pers comm]
WFT6066B	AD 1651	AD 1779	-	8.44	London City Whitefriars [I Tyers pers comm]
SWED_HRJ	AD 1349	AD 1788	-	8.95	Härjedalen [Bartholin pers comm]

Table 3. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the two average curves for pine for the bulwark and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

A second pine group, group 2, included four samples. Only three of these are included in the average however, as the fourth, sample P12, is clearly from a tree growing under quite different conditions as the other three. It is a much older tree and has had much slower growth. The average SE06M002 is 135 years long and covers the period AD 1614-1748. As can be seen from the table of t -values achieved between this average and tree-ring datasets for pines for Northern Europe (table 3) the highest correlations appear chiefly with Scandinavian chronologies. The trees forming group 2 might have come from north of Stockholm.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. To estimate the felling dates of the trees a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. Several calculations of the average sapwood in oaks in different regions in Northern Europe have been published, and as the provenance of the oaks used to build the ship at Skeppsholmen is likely to be Småland, I have here chosen to use a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein

1980)) and for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)). There is no published sapwood statistic for Sweden, as far as I am aware.

In pine and spruce using the number of sapwood rings to estimate the felling date in the absence of bark edge is highly problematical, due to the wide variation in the number of sapwood rings. It can also be difficult to identify the sapwood edge in waterlogged archaeological conifer timbers. Sapwood has therefore not been recorded in this analysis, and felling, in the absence of bark edge, is placed at after the date of the outermost preserved tree-ring.

In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Waterfront											
SE06001a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p13 grop17 pæl PISY	94			C	0	W	W	N	1,45	undated
SE060029	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p3 grop9 liggende kranbro PISY	118	AD 1657	AD 1774	C	0	W	O	N	1,36	AD 1774 winter
SE06003a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p12 grop4 x13x8x PISY	214	AD 1530	AD 1743	C	0	W	W	N	0,87	AD 1743 winter
SE06004a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p15 pole1 PCAB	76	AD 1699	AD 1774	C	0	?	W	N	2,01	AD 1774-75?
SE06005a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p14 liggende kaj PCAB	81			C	0	?	W	N	2,11	Undated
SE06006a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p4 liggende kran PISY	120	AD 1656	AD 1775	C	0	N	W	N	1,22	after AD 1775
SE06007a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p6 stående pæl PISY	105	AD 1624	AD 1728	C	0	W	W	N	1,74	AD 1728 winter
SE06008a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p5 stående pæl PISY	113	AD 1614	AD 1726	C	0	N	W	H1	1,41	after AD 1727
SE06009a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p2 stående pæl kran PISY	58	AD 1688	AD 1745	C	0	?	W	N	2,00	AD 1745-46?
SE06010a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p16 pæl PISY	107	AD 1642	AD 1748	C	0	W	W	N	1,03	AD 1748 winter
Ship											
Z2070019	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p21 T6 bottenstock QUSP	168	AD 1442	AD 1609	F	3	N	O	S1	1,10	AD 1616-31
Z207002a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p9 grop 9 plank QUSP same tree as p11	126	AD 1487	AD 1612	G	14	Y	T	N	1,56	AD 1612-13
Z207003a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p1 grop 9 bottenstock QUSP	164	AD 1434	AD 1597	G	0	N	Q	H1	1,96	after AD 1608
Z207004a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p17 T4 bottenstock QUSP	101	AD 1507	AD 1607	G	6	N	Q	S1	2,59	AD 1611-26
Z207005a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p19 T3 bottenstock QUSP	80			G	10	½ s/s	Q	N	2,88	undated
Z207006a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p7 grop 9 kattspår QUSP	104	AD 1509	AD 1612	C	12	½ s/s	O	N	2,04	AD 1613 spring
Z207007a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p20 T5 bottenstock QUSP	185	AD 1413	AD 1597	G	0	N	O	H1	0,88	after AD 1608
Z207008a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p10 grop 9 intimmer QUSP	127	AD 1487	AD 1613	C	12	W	Q	N	1,33	AD 1613 winter
Z207009a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p22 T1 bottenstock QUSP	54	AD 1556	AD 1609	G	5	N	O	S1	1,14	AD 1614-29
Z207010a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p18 bordlægning QUSP	60			G	0	N	T	H1	1,26	undated
Z207011a	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p8 spant QUSP	98	AD 1514	AD 1611	C	11	N	S	N	1,25	AD 1615-30
Averages											
SE06M001	Stockholm Skeppsholmen 3 timbers PISY	120	AD 1656	AD 1775						1,44	
SE06M002	Stockholm Skeppsholmen 3 timbers PISY	135	AD 1614	AD 1748						1,47	
Z207M002	Stockholm Skeppsholmen wreck 9 timbers QUSP	201	AD 1413	AD 1613						1,53	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			7 October 2017								

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Daly, Aoife, 2017. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck and waterfront at Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. *dendro.dk report 2017:54*, Copenhagen.

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